

How to locate the Campanian Ignimbrite site Urluia based on literature? How to provide and publish this data in a FAIR way?

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Abstract. This short paper describes the georeferencing of the Urluia Campanian Ignimbrite (CI) site in Romania.

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1 INTRODUCTION

The Campanian Ignimbrite (CI) ash airfall in Central Europe, a trachytic tuff, was derived from a Late Pleistocene volcanic event [5, 1] in the Campania region. Around 40'000 years ago, the largest eruption of the CI took place in the Phlegraean Fields (Fig. 1). Based on this, massive glass deposits from the CI-eruption covered large parts of the eastern European continent (Fig. 2); volcanic material of the CI is often found in isolated watersheds and valleys.

These findspots are recorded in several papers, e.g. (a) precise coordinates, e.g. "[...] Lago Grande di Monticchio in southern Italy (40°56'N, 15°35'E)" [3], (b) references to cities, e.g. Naples [11], (c) or references to regions, e.g. Altopiano delle Murge [8] or Castelcivita Cave [6]. One of these findspots is "the site of Urluia Quarry on the Dobrogea loess plateau [...], some 15 km south of the Danube River." [7].

Figure 1: Graphic of deposit dispersal during the Campanian Ignimbrite Eruption 40,000 years ago based on [10]. Wikirictor, CC BY-SA 4.0, via Wikimedia Commons.

Figure 2: Sample of Campanian Ignimbrite Findspots based on several literature. Florian Thiery and Fiona Schenk, CC BY 4.0.

2 FINDSPOT URLUIA

The location of the CI findspot Urluia is mentioned in several papers. Fitzsimmons et al. [7] write "In this paper we investigate [...] the site of Urluia Quarry on the Dobrogea loess plateau [...], some 15 km south of the Danube River. The site immediately overlies the Quaternary-uplifted Cretaceous-Tertiary-age limestone basement rocks [(Munteanu et al., 2008)], which were the target of earlier quarrying activities." Pötter et al. [12] uses this information but added the following: "The Urluia (URL) LPS is located in an abandoned limestone quarry on the limestone plateau of the Dobrogea [(Fitzsimmons et al., 2013; Fitzsimmons and Hambach, 2014; Obreht et al., 2017)].".

A closer look at the resources of the World Wide Web shows that gazetteers such as Geonames lead to the wrong location: the village of Urluia (<https://www.geonames.org/664132/urluia.html>, located at 44.1043, 27.9146). By using the information of Pötter et al. [12] that the site is located in an abandoned limestone quarry, Open Street Map (OSM) helps. The quarry is modelled as a way (<http://www.openstreetmap.org/way/84975654>). From this point, in ca. 17km bee-line, the Danube River appears (Fig. 3). This information helps to georeference the CI Urluia findspot to epsg:4326 POINT(27.9021 44.0947). In this case, only four decimal places are used to model and visualise the precision.

Figure 3: OSM maps to locate the Urluia CI findspot. Florian Thiery, CC BY 4.0.

3 MODELLING AS LINKED OPEN DATA

To model the aforementioned process and publish all the 'hidden assumptions' behind the georeferencing methods Linked Open Data can be used [13, 14, 9, 2]. For this purpose the "Fuzzy Spatial Locations Ontology" (fuzzy-sl-ontology) has been created and is currently under development (see <https://github.com/Research-Squirrel-Engineers/fuzzy-sl-ontology>). This ontology is based on PROV-O, SKOS and GeoSPARQL [4]. The PROV-O model defines three basic classes: Entity, Activity and Agent. Transferred to the georeferencing task, the entity is a site (modelled with another GeoSPARQL node), the activity is the method used, and the agent is the person who has done the job (Fig. 4). Using this lightweight ontology, the georeferencing task of Urluia can be executed. The modelling result can be seen in CI Site 52 (https://research-squirrel-engineers.github.io/campanian-ignimbrite-geo/cisite_52/index.html) and Fig. 5 / Fig. 6.

Figure 4: Simple structure of the Fuzzy Spatial Locations Ontology. Florian Thiery, CC BY 4.0.

Figure 5: CI Site Urluia located near the abandoned limestone quarry. Florian Thieri, CC BY 4.0.

Property	Value
<code>certaintyDesc</code> (fsl:certaintyDesc)	findspot mentioned in a scientific paper (rdf:langString) (iso6391:en)
<code>certaintyLevel</code> (fsl:certaintyLevel)	medium (fsl:medium) [x]
<code>hasReference</code> (fsl:hasReference)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Fitzsimmons et al., 2014, 2013 (xsd:string) Obrecht et al., 2017 (xsd:string) Potter et al., 2021 (xsd:string)
<code>partOf</code> (fsl:partOf)	CampanianIgmimbriteProject (fsl:CampanianIgmimbriteProject) [x]
<code>siteType</code> (fsl:siteType)	ArchaeologicalSite (fsl:ArchaeologicalSite) [x]
<code>spatialType</code> (fsl:spatialType)	InhabitedPlace (fsl:InhabitedPlace) [x]
<code>hasGeometry</code> (gsp:hasGeometry)	cisite_52_geom (fsl:cisite_52_geom)
<code>type</code> (rdf:type)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Entity (prov:Entity) [x] Place (pleiades:Place) [x] Site (fsl:Site) [x]
<code>comment</code> (rdfs:comment)	CI findspot related from literature (rdf:langString) (iso6391:en)
<code>label</code> (rdfs:label)	Urluia (Romania) (rdf:langString) (iso6391:en)
<code>closeMatch</code> (skos:closeMatch)	664132 (gns:664132) [x]
<code>prefLabel</code> (skos:prefLabel)	Urluia (Romania) (rdf:langString) (iso6391:en)
<code>scopeNote</code> (skos:scopeNote)	CI findspot related from literature (rdf:langString) (iso6391:en)
<code>is member of</code> (rdfs:member) of	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Entity Instances Collection (fsl:Entity_collection) Place Instances Collection (fsl:Place_collection) Site Instances Collection (fsl:Site_collection)
<code>is used</code> (prov:used) of	cisite_52_activity (fsl:cisite_52_activity)

Metadata

Property	Value
<code>creator</code> (terms:creator)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 0000-0002-3246-3531 [x] 0000-0003-1100-6494 [x]
<code>license</code> (terms:license)	4.0 [x]
<code>rightsHolder</code> (terms:rightsHolder)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 0000-0002-3246-3531 [x] 0000-0003-1100-6494 [x]
<code>wasAttributedTo</code> (prov:wasAttributedTo)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 0009-0008-2877-3204 (orcid:0009-0008-2877-3204) [x] Cl.py [x]
<code>wasDerivedFrom</code> (prov:wasDerivedFrom)	campanian-igmimbrite-geo [x]
<code>wasGeneratedBy</code> (prov:wasGeneratedBy)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> cisite_52_activity (fsl:cisite_52_activity) cisite_52_pyscript (fsl:cisite_52_pyscript)

Figure 6: CI Site Urluia modelled using the fuzzy-sl-ontology. Florian Thieri, CC BY 4.0.

REFERENCES

- [1] Barberi, F.; Innocenti, F.; Lirer, L.; Munno, R.; Pescatore, T.; Santacroce, R.: The Campanian Ignimbrite: A major prehistoric eruption in the Neapolitan area (Italy). *Bulletin of Volcanology*, 41, 1978.
- [2] Berners-Lee, T.: *Linked Data - Design Issues*, 2006. <https://www.w3.org/DesignIssues/LinkedData.html>.
- [3] Brauer, A.; Mingram, J.; Frank, U.; Günter, C.; Georg Schettler; Wulf, S.; Zolitschka, B.; Negen-dank, J.F.: Abrupt environmental oscillations during the Early Weichselian recorded at Lago Grande di Monticchio, southern Italy. *Quaternary International*, 73-74, 79–90, 2000. ISSN 10406182. [http://doi.org/10.1016/S1040-6182\(00\)00066-5](http://doi.org/10.1016/S1040-6182(00)00066-5).
- [4] Car, N.J.; Homburg, T.: GeoSPARQL 1.1: Motivations, Details and Applications of the Decadal Update to the Most Important Geospatial LOD Standard. *ISPRS International Journal of Geo-Information*, 11(2), 117, 2022. ISSN 2220-9964. <http://doi.org/10.3390/ijgi11020117>.
- [5] De Vivo, B.; Rolandi, G.; Gans, P.B.; Calvert, A.; Bohron, W.A.; Spera, F.J.; Belkin, H.E.: New constraints on the pyroclastic eruptive history of the Campanian volcanic Plain (Italy). *Mineralogy and Petrology*, 73(1-3), 47–65, 2001. ISSN 0930-0708, 1438-1168. <http://doi.org/10.1007/s007100170010>.
- [6] Fedele, F.G.; Giaccio, B.; Hajdas, I.: Timescales and cultural process at 40,000 BP in the light of the Campanian Ignimbrite eruption, Western Eurasia. *Journal of Human Evolution*, 55(5), 834–857, 2008. ISSN 00472484. <http://doi.org/10.1016/j.jhevol.2008.08.012>.
- [7] Fitzsimmons, K.E.; Hambach, U.: Loess accumulation during the last glacial maximum: Evidence from Urluia, southeastern Romania. *Quaternary International*, 334-335, 74–85, 2014. ISSN 10406182. <http://doi.org/10.1016/j.quaint.2013.08.005>.
- [8] Giaccio, B.; Isaia, R.; Fedele, F.G.; Di Canzio, E.; Hoffecker, J.; Ronchitelli, A.; Sinitsyn, A.A.; Anikovich, M.; Lisitsyn, S.N.; Popov, V.V.: The Campanian Ignimbrite and Codola tephra layers: Two temporal/stratigraphic markers for the Early Upper Palaeolithic in southern Italy and eastern Europe. *Journal of Volcanology and Geothermal Research*, 177(1), 208–226, 2008. ISSN 03770273. <http://doi.org/10.1016/j.jvolgeores.2007.10.007>.
- [9] Isaksen, L.: *Archaeology and the Semantic Web*. Thesis (Doctoral), University of Southampton, School of Electronics and Computer Science, 2011. <https://eprints.soton.ac.uk/id/eprint/206421>.
- [10] Marti, A.; Folch, A.; Costa, A.; Engwell, S.: Reconstructing the plinian and co-ignimbrite sources of large volcanic eruptions: A novel approach for the Campanian Ignimbrite. *Scientific Reports*, 6(1), 21220, 2016. ISSN 2045-2322. <http://doi.org/10.1038/srep21220>.
- [11] Orsi, G.; De Vita, S.; Di Vito, M.: The restless, resurgent Campi Flegrei nested caldera (Italy): constraints on its evolution and configuration. *Journal of Volcanology and Geothermal Research*, 74(3-4), 179–214, 1996. ISSN 03770273. [http://doi.org/10.1016/S0377-0273\(96\)00063-7](http://doi.org/10.1016/S0377-0273(96)00063-7).
- [12] Pötter, S.; Veres, D.; Baykal, Y.; Nett, J.J.; Schulte, P.; Hambach, U.; Lehmkuhl, F.: Disentangling Sedimentary Pathways for the Pleniglacial Lower Danube Loess Based on Geochemical Signatures. *Frontiers in Earth Science*, 9, 600010, 2021. ISSN 2296-6463. <http://doi.org/10.3389/feart.2021.600010>.
- [13] Schmidt, S.C.; Thiery, F.; Trognitz, M.: Practices of Linked Open Data in Archaeology and Their Realisation in Wikidata. *Digital*, 2(3), 333–364, 2022. ISSN 2673-6470. <http://doi.org/10.3390/digital2030019>.
- [14] Thiery, F.: *Semantic Web und Linked Data: Generierung von Interoperabilität in archäologischen Fachdaten am Beispiel römischer Töpferstempel*. *Squirrel Papers*, 4(1), No.3, 2013. <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.292979>.